

COMMON RINGS. PART I. *c*'s-ELIMINATIONS

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Based on stereochemical considerations, it has been pointed out that the ease of ionic 1:2 *cis*-eliminations in various suitably constituted derivatives of common rings should follow the order: cyclopentane $\approx$ cycloheptane > cyclohexane. Qualitative data are presented, which appear to support this hypothesis.

*cyclo*Alkanes and their derivatives form a unique series, wherein the differences in the various chemical and physical properties of a given class of compounds arise essentially as a consequence of the three dimensional geometry of the rings. This concept has been advocated, especially, by Prelog *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 420) and Brown and his co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 212; 1952, 74, 1894; Brown, *Record of Chemical Progress*, 1953, 14, 83) to explain the differences in the behaviour of the various members differing in ring-size. The treatment, apparently, is not satisfactory in the case of small-ring compounds, where other factors must also be operative (Roberts and Chambers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5034).

In the common rings*, Baeyer's classical strain (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2269, 2277) is almost absent and the differences in the energy-content (Spitzer and Huffman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 211) arise essentially* from the non-bonded interactions of the polymethylene chain. While preserving the tetrahedral valency angles, the cyclopentane ring can be built only from the energetically unfavourable, eclipsed constellations (conformations) of the polymethylene chain; according to Pitzer (*Science*, 1945, 101, 672) this geometrically preferred model of cyclopentane does not visualise the actual picture of the molecule, which can gain extra stability by assuming a non-planar conformation (Fig. 1), when the strain due to non-bonded interactions (Pitzer strain) will be somewhat relieved.

For cyclohexane, the chair conformation (Fig. 2) has been shown to be more stable, both on thermodynamic considerations (Aston *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2029; Beckett *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1947, 69, 2188) and on physical evidence (Rasmussen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1943, 11, 249; Hassel and Viervoll, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1947,

* The classification of ring-compounds into small rings (3- & 4-membered), common-rings (5-, 6- & 7-membered), medium rings (8- to 12-membered) and large rings (13-membered and larger) as suggested by Profs. Brown and Prelog (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 215; foot-note 21) is adopted.

1, 149; et seq.). *cyclo*Heptane ring, like *cyclo*hexane, can also exist in two strainless (classical) non-planar constellations; from models it can be qualitatively deduced that the chair conformation (Fig. 3) will have lesser Pitzer-strain (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 4) to the extent of about 2.8 k. cal.*

In the transition state of a chemical reaction requiring a synchronous action, the various atoms of importance must occupy a planar configuration for maximum efficiency; this is undoubtedly due to the efficient overlapping of the concerned orbitals which can result from such a configuration. Barton and co-workers have pointed out the importance of such a concept for various 1:2-*trans*-eliminations (Barton and Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1066; Barton and Rosenfelder, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1048; Barton, *ibid.*, 1953, 1027) and this theory has been utilised by several workers to rationalise various E₂-type eliminations (Cristol and Hause, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2193; Evans and Shoppe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 540), S_N2-type Wagner substitutions (Hiskey, Hirschmann and Wendler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5135; Hirschmann *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 4013; Elks *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1739; Ames *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 1905), E₂-Wagner-eliminations (e.g., see cases cited by Hirschmann *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), Tiffeneau rearrangement (McCasland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2293; Pollak and Curtin, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 961; Ramirez and Stafiej, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 134) and deaminations (Mills, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 260; Cremlyn *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 1847). The much enhanced solvolysis rate of *isobornyl* chloride, as compared to that of *bornyl* chloride, has also been explained by Winstein *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1127) as being due to the co-planarity of the atoms involved in the case of *isobornyl* halide (cf. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2845).

This importance of co-planarity of the centres concerned has also been stressed in the case of E₁-eliminations (Barton, *ibid.*, 1949, 2174; Barton and Rosenfelder, *loc. cit.*). Thus, in reactions involving 1:2-*cis*-eliminations, the transition state (A) must have a planar configuration.

By considering the above models of common rings, it can be seen that, whereas in the case of *cyclopentane* and *cycloheptane*, the four atoms (2 carbons and 2 *cis*-substituents) of importance for a *cis*-elimination can acquire a co-planar configuration without altering the preferred constellations of the rings, the corresponding *cyclohexane* analogue cannot do so. Thus, in the case of a *cyclohexane* derivative, the configuration of the transition state will differ appreciably from that of the ground state, whereas no such difference will exist in the case of the corresponding five- and seven-

* Prof. R. B. Turner has kindly informed the author that this value is quite reasonable.

membered analogues. This will be reflected in a higher activation energy* for the cyclohexane derivative, and consequently in this system 1:2-*cis*-eliminations should be slower as compared to those in the analogous cyclopentane and cycloheptane compounds. Of course, this does not apply to those cyclohexane derivatives, in which the ring has been forced to acquire the boat conformation [e.g., when locked by the presence of a 1:4-bridge or by incorporation in a suitable tricyclic system; cf., Shoppee, *Chem & Ind.*, 1952, 86].

Conversely, 1:2-*trans*-eliminations should be faster in a cyclohexyl derivative (with axial disposition of the substituents) as compared to those in an analogous compound with five-membered ring.

Another factor, which will influence the rate of an elimination reaction, is the ease with which the common rings will accommodate an ethylenic linkage. From the heats of hydrogenation of simple cyclic mono-olefines (for data vide Ketelaar, "Chemical Constitution", Elsevier Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1953, p. 205) it may be concluded that the ease of incorporation of the olefinic linkage will decrease in the order:

Thus, this second factor should facilitate 1:2-elimination in the cycloheptane and cyclopentane rings relative to the cyclohexane system. In a *cis*-elimination, both these factors will operate in the same direction so as to enhance the elimination rate in the seven- and five-membered rings.

In order to test this hypothesis, some comparative *cis*-eliminations have been carried out (*vide infra*) and the results appear to support the predicted behaviour of the common rings. A superior data on this could have been obtained by a kinetic study of a unimolecular *cis*-elimination reaction taking place at temperatures not exceeding 100°. It is realised that at higher temperatures (required for the pyrolysis of esters) the expected energy-hill difference will tend to become less prominent, more so, because at elevated temperatures the boat conformation of cyclohexane assumes importance (Beckett *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). However, the qualitative data presented definitely point towards the correctness of the hypothesis.

Pyrolysis of Cyanohydrin Acetates

It is now well established that the pyrolysis of acetates to yield olefines and acetic acid is a unimolecular reaction, which proceeds by a *cis*-elimination mechanism (Hurd and Blunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2419; Barton, *loc. cit.*; Alexander and Mundrak,

* This extra activation energy may be estimated roughly by determining the difference in the energy content between the chair conformation of cyclohexane and the next stable conformation of cyclohexane having at least one "eclipsed" interaction of the *n*-butane type. A study of the models reveals that such an arrangement can only be the boat conformation of cyclohexane. Thus, the difference in the energy-content of the chair and boat constellations [5.6 k. cal. Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2128] can be a measure of the extra activation energy.

J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1950, **72**, 1810, 3194; 1951, **73**, 59]. The decomposition of the cyanohydrin acetates of *cyclopentanone*, *cyclohexanone* and *suberone* has been investigated under exactly identical conditions and the results* obtained (Table I) are in agreement with the theory outlined above.

TABLE I

No.	Temp.	Δ^1 - <i>cyclo</i> Pentenylnitrile.	Δ^1 - <i>cyclo</i> Hexenylnitrile. (% yield per pass)	Δ^1 - <i>cyclo</i> Heptenylnitrile.
1.	440° ± 2°	65.8	59.0	82.6
		67.0	59.1	82.0
2.	460° ± 2°	92.0	80.0	93.6
		90.0	79.0	91.4

The above results also reveal the superiority of the cyanohydrin acetate decomposition method for the preparation of unsaturated nitriles of the common rings; the overall yields based on the starting ketone are over 80% (vide Experimental).

Decomposition of Borates

Brandenberg and Galat (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3275) reported the use of boric acid for the dehydration of alcohols; O'Connor and Nace (*ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 2118) later suggested that this reaction proceeded *via* the unstable metaborate esters, which underwent *cis*-elimination to yield the olefine:

This reaction** has been applied to the dehydration of the *cycloalkanol*s of the common rings and the results obtained have been recorded in Table II, and the order of decomposition temperatures is the expected one.

* In the advance communication on the pyrolysis of *cyclopentanone* cyanohydrin acetate (Dev, *Exper.*, 1954, 10, 60) comparison with the pyrolysis of *cyclohexane* cyanohydrin acetate was based on the published data (Burus *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 400); the slightly different results described are more stable, as the comparative decomposition of the acetates has been carried out under exactly identical condition.

**The preparation of the meta-borates is more conveniently carried out by azeotropic distillation (vide Experimental) with toluene. The pyrolysis of the borates should prove to be the method of choice for the dehydration of alcohols, especially secondary and primary. It is hoped to determine the scope of this reaction in a future communication.

TABLE II

	Metaborate of		
	<i>cyclopentanol.</i>	<i>cyclohexanol.</i>	<i>cycloheptanol.</i>
Decomp. temp. (initial)	220°	235-240°	220-225°
Decomp. temp. ("progress")	185°-190°	215°	200°

Light Absorption Data

The ultraviolet spectra of the Δ^1 -nitriles and the acids and esters derived from them are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

Light absorption for

n.	X = CN.		X = COOEt.		X = COOH.	
	λ max.	ϵ .	λ max.	ϵ .	λ max.	ϵ .
1.	214 m μ	10,090	223 m μ	8,654	† 221 m μ	10, 280
2.	< 211 *	11,290	219	11,260	{ † 216 218	{ 0 210 10, 270
3.	214	10,310	221	9,854	† 220	9, 057

* Cf. Braude and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 327.

† Cf. Braude and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1951, 1755; 1950, 2014; 1953, 2204; Ungnade and Ortega, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 1564.

These data indicate that the *cyclopentane* and *cycloheptane* derivatives of this type show a bathochromic shift of approximately 4 ± 2 m μ as compared to the corresponding *cyclohexane* compounds. A search of the literature reveals that this conclusion applies to various other cases with (X = CHO, COCH₃, COC₆H₅, C $\equiv$ CH, etc.). A complete discussion of this will form the subject matter of a further communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined in 95% ethanol solution on a Beckman spectrophotometer (Model DU). Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 40°-60°.

cyclopentanone Cyanohydrin Acetate.—To thoroughly chilled (ice-salt) *cyclopentanone* (126 g., 1.5 M) liquid HCN (48.6 g., 75 c.c., 1.8 M) was added in one lot. To this powdered potassium cyanide (0.2 g.) and diethylamine (0.2 c.c.) were introduced, and after keeping the mixture at -10° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, it was allowed to stand in the Frigidairé for 24 hours. The product was chilled to -5° and the base neutralised* by the addition of phosphoric acid (85%, 1 c.c.). After dilution with anhydrous ether (75 c.c.), the material was again well chilled and a mixture (also cooled to about -5°)

of acetic anhydride (240 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (10 c.c.) added. This was left aside at 0° for 48 hours and then at room temperature (25°-30°) for another 4½ days. The excess acetic anhydride, etc. were removed through a column (Vigreux; 8") and the residue carefully fractionated to obtain the required compound as a colorless, mobile liquid, b. p. 120°/15 mm., 137°/30 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4455; yield 216-223 g. (94-97%). The acetate can be distilled without any decomposition; b.p. 226-27°/684 mm. A purified sample (refractionation, central cut) had n_D^{20} 1.4460; d_4^{20} 1.053; M_b , 38.77 (calc. 38.35). (Found: C, 62.6; H, 7.5. $C_8H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 62.7; H, 7.2 per cent).

When the reaction mixture was worked up before acetylation, the cyanohydrin could be isolated in 92-94% yield; b.p. 130°/26 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4555. A purified sample had n_D^{20} 1.4540; d_4^{20} 1.022; M_b , 29.41 (calc. 28.99) (Cook and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 959, report b.p. 126°/26 mm.).

cycloHexanone cyanohydrin acetate was prepared exactly as above; b.p. 148-49°/35 mm., m.p. 48-49°, yield 91-94%. A sample was recrystallised from *n*-hexane in large colorless prisms, m.p. 48-50° [Burns, Jones and Ritchie, *loc. cit.*, report 45.8% yield, m.p. 48-49°].

cycloHeptanone Cyanohydrin Acetate.—By following the procedure outlined above for the *cyclopentanone* derivative, the seven-membered analogue was obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 163°/37 mm., 146°/15 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4650, yield 91-95%. [Found: N, 7.9. $C_{10}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 7.7 per cent].

Pyrolysis of Cyanohydrin Acetates.—One end of a thick Pyrex-tube (50 cm; I.D. 1.9 cm.) was bent at an angle of 120°, and to the other end another tubing (45 cm; I.D. 0.9 cm.) carrying a B-19 cone was fused; the cone fitted into a Y-shaped adapter, which, in turn, was connected to a water-condenser and a receiver. The wider-tube was filled with broken Pyrex-glass chips (average length 1 cm.) to a length of 20 cm. (measured from the constriction). The packed portion of the tube was heated in an electric furnace; the required temperature (as determined by a thermocouple) was maintained by a Sunvic control. The furnace, carrying the pyrolysis tube, was held at a slight angle (about 20°).

The pyrolysis at the required temperature was carried out by dropping in the cyanohydrin acetate (0.15 M) during 11 minutes; the addition was made in three or four lots so that the temperature and the time could be effectively controlled. The receiver was cooled in an ice-bath. After the pyrolysis, the furnace was allowed to cool to about 100° and *n*-hexane (15 c.c.) was let in as a "chaser" to remove the last traces of the material. The product (pyrolysate + "chasings") was taken up in petroleum ether (50 c.c.), washed with water (50 c.c.) and finally with brine (50 c.c. × 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed (column) and the residue carefully fractionated through a Vigreux column with a total-condensation-type still head. The results are recorded in Table I.

Δ^1 -*cycloPentenylnitrile*.—For preparative purposes, the pyrolysis was best carried out at around 470°; 2 g. of the acetate was let in during one minute. In this way the unsaturated nitrile was obtained in 95-98% yield. The product, which had a strong odour of bitter almonds had b.p. 88-89°/54 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4670-1.4690. A purified sample (refractionation; central cut) gave b.p. 75°/35 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4700 (Cook and Linstead,

loc. cit., obtained this nitrile by the dehydration of the cyanohydrin with thionyl chloride in benzene and the yield was 55-60% and b.p. 69°/15 mm. Also vide Baker and Leeds, *ibid.*, 1948, 977).

Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl nitrile was prepared in 93-97% yield by conducting the pyrolysis of the cyanohydrin acetate at about 480° and by passing the acetate at the rate of .2 g./min. (cf. Burns, Jones and Ritchie, *loc. cit.*). The material had b.p. 118°/65 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4780-1.4770 and possessed an intense odour of bitter almonds. A purified sample had b.p. 99°/35 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4780 [Kidd, Robins and Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3244, prepared the nitrile in 94% yield by the dehydration of the cyanohydrin with phosphoryl chloride in pyridine; b.p. 85-90°/17 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4864. Cf. Ruzicka and Brugger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 399; Bhattacharyya, *this Journal*, 1945, 22, 87].

Δ^1 -cycloheptenyl Nitrile.—By following the conditions stated above for the five-membered analogue, the cycloheptenyl nitrile was obtained in 96-99% yield. This had only a mild odour of bitter almonds and had b.p. 116-18°/35 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4845-1.4850. A refractionated sample gave b.p. 118°/35 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4850. (Found: N, 11.24. $C_7H_{11}N$ requires N, 11.54 per cent).

Ethyl cycloalkenyl carboxylates were obtained from the corresponding nitriles (0.12 M) by heating them with absolute ethyl alcohol (80 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (C.P., 20 c.c.) on a steam-bath for 24 hours (silica-gel guard tube). The coloured (orange to brown) reaction mixture, which deposited a lot of ammonium sulphate on cooling, was diluted with water (250 c.c.) with ice-cooling. The ester layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with petroleum ether (30 c.c. $\times$ 3). The combined extracts were mixed with the main lot and washed with brine (25 c.c. $\times$ 3) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The material was stripped off the solvent and the residue fractionated through a helices-packed column (6") with a total-condensation-type still head. The esters were colorless oils with pleasant odour; yield 70-75%.

The ethyl Δ^1 -cyclopentenyl carboxylate had b.p. 95°/35 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4600 (Cook and Lins'ead, *loc. cit.*, reported b.p. 92°/25 mm.).

Ethyl Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl carboxylate gave b.p. 109°/35 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4695 (Gardner and Rydon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 48, recorded b.p. 95-97°/15 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4716).

Ethyl Δ^1 -cycloheptenyl carboxylate had b.p. 125°/35 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4770. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 9.4. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.4; H, 9.5 per cent). As is apparent from the light absorption data (Table III), as well as the acid hydrolysis to the parent acids (*vide infra*), the ethyl esters prepared by the above procedure are essentially pure Δ^1 -isomers.

cycloAlk 1-ene-carboxylic acids were prepared by two methods: (i) Acid hydrolysis of the ester and (ii) alkaline hydrolysis of the nitrile.

Method (i).—The unsaturated ester (0.1M), HCl (C. P., 50 c.c.), acetic acid (25 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.) were mixed and gently refluxed for five hours. In the case of cyclopent-1-ene-carboxylic acid, the reaction mixture was chilled to 0° for several hours and the acid, m.p. 120-22°, collected by filtration, yield 85-90%. A sample was recrystallised from *n*-heptane in white prisms, m.p. 122-23° (Haworth and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894,

65, 101, report m.p. 119-21°). The other two acids were isolated by diluting the reaction mixture with water (100 c.c.), followed by extraction with ether (50 c.c. × 3). The combined extracts were washed with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution (10%; 50 c.c. × 3) and the ammoniacal extract acidified with hydrochloric acid, saturated with sodium chloride, and the acid taken up in petroleum ether (50 c.c. × 3). The petroleum ether solution was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was flashed off (column) and the residue fractionated. The cyclohex-1-ene-carboxylic acid was obtained as an oil, which crystallised on chilling, b.p. 130°/6 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4990; m.p. 33-35°, yield 80%. A sample was recrystallised from petroleum ether at -10° as colorless prisms, m.p. 37-38° (Von Auwers and Krullpfeiffer, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1396, report m.p. 38-39°; Braude and Coles, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 37°; Kidd, Robins and Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3244; b.p. 138-41°/18 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5010). The cyclohept-1-ene-carboxylic acid was isolated in 75% yield, b.p. 117°/1 mm., m.p. 47-48.5°. A sample was recrystallised from *n*-hexane as white plates, m.p. 49-50° (Willstätter, *Annalen*, 1901, 317, 239, reported m.p. 50-51°; Braude, Forbes and Evans, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 49°).

Method (ii).—The unsaturated nitrile (0.12M) was gently refluxed with KOH (13.4 g., 0.24 M) in water (130 c.c.) for 40 hours. The cooled solution was acidified to p_H 2.0 with HCl (conc.) and the separated acid isolated as above. cyclopent-1-ene-carboxylic acid was obtained in 62% yield, m.p. 120-22°, and cyclohex-1-ene-carboxylic acid in a yield of 80%; n_D^{20} 1.4975, m.p. 27-28°; the cyclohept-1-ene-carboxylic acid was prepared in a yield of 77-80% and had m.p. 42-46°. These constants indicated that some isomerisation of the Δ^1 - to the Δ^2 -isomer had taken place under the alkaline conditions in the cyclohexene and cycloheptene acids.

Pyrolysis of Borates.—A mixture of the alcohol (0.5 M), boric acid (0.5 M) and toluene (50 c.c.) was placed in a flask (300 c.c.), which carried a thermometer, well reaching to almost the bottom of the flask; a modified Dean-Stark apparatus (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1953, 80, 443) was attached, and the mixture gently refluxed with continuous removal of water. The separation of water (about 19 c.c.) generally ceased after about 3 hours, when the toluene was distilled off, first as such, later under vacuum (water-pump); the temperature of the bath was not allowed to rise beyond 120°-140°. The residue, which represented the metaborate, crystallised out on cooling.

To the flask containing the borate, a fractionating column (Vigreux, 35 cm., vacuum insulated and carrying a total-condensation-type still head) was attached and the borate slowly heated. In the case of cyclopentanol and cycloheptanol, the esters melted at about 80° and 100° (inside temperature) respectively, whereas the cyclohexyl borate melted at 215°-225°. On further heating, the decomposition started with the generation of the olefine; these temperatures ("initial") have been recorded in Table II; immediately below (about 5°) these temperatures, the esters appeared to boil without decomposition. As the pyrolysis proceeded, the inside temperature fell and the distillation of the olefine was quite smooth at a much lower temperature ("Temperature of decomposition progress"—Table II). The distillate was worked up for isolation of the olefine.

cyclopentene.—The distillate, which was collected in a receiver cooled in an ice-salt-bath, contained traces of water and was dried over activated silica gel (-100 mesh;

3 g.) at 0° for several hours, and then fractionated over sodium (some dry xylene was used to wash out the silica gel; the xylene also served as a "chaser"). The olefine was collected at 41°/684 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4208; yield 88-90% (McCasland and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2193, report b p. 43-46; n_D^{20} 1.4218. Cf. Kogl and Ultee, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1950, 69, 1582).

cycloHexene, b.p. 78-80°/684 mm., was similarly isolated in a yield of 90%.

cycloHeptene.—In this case petrol fraction (30°-40°) was used in place of xylene for removing the last traces of the olefine from the silica gel. The material had b.p. 110-11°/684 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4575, yield 85% (Kohler *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1059, report b.p. 114.38°/760 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4580. Cf. Jackson, *ibid.*, 1933, 55, 4284; Boeseken and Hanegraef, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1942, 61, 69).

cycloHeptanol required for these investigations was prepared from suberone by the following methods of reduction.

(i) *By Meerwein-Ponndorf Reduction.*—The reduction was carried out by closely following the procedure described for the preparation of 5-oxybenzosubaran [Sukh Dev, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 799]. The acetone-test became negative after about 42 hours. The product was isolated by extraction with petroleum ether, washing with brine, drying (Na_2SO_4) and fractionation; b.p. 180°/684 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4725, yield 88-90%.

(ii) *By Lithium Aluminium Hydride Reduction.*—Suberone (22.4 g., 0.2 M) was reduced with LiAlH_4 (2.85 g., 0.075 M) in anhydrous ether (150 c.c.) in the usual manner; yield 97-99%.

(iii) *Sodium-isoPropanol Reduction.*—In an one-litre 3-necked flask, sodium (13.8 g., 0.6 g. atom) was covered with toluene (80 c.c.). This was heated in an oil-bath (120°-130°) till the sodium melted; the flame was removed and with vigorous stirring a mixture of the ketone (22.4 g., 0.2 M) and isopropyl alcohol (36 g., 0.6 M) was introduced during 15 minutes (so that the refluxing was controllable); toluene (20 c.c.) was used to wash in the last traces of the ketone-alcohol mixture. The colorless reaction mixture was stirred and refluxed (under nitrogen atmosphere) till all the sodium disappeared (about one hour). The product was cooled in ice and cautiously treated with ice-water (about 500 c.c.). The toluene layer was separated, the aqueous phase extracted with petroleum ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and added on to the main lot, which was washed with brine (50 c.c. $\times$ 3) and dried. The solvent was removed (column) and the residue fractionated; b.p. 180°/684 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4740, yield 85-90%.

Light Absorption Measurement.—In view of the work of Ungnade and Ortega (*loc. cit.*) the spectra were taken on approximately 0.5×10^{-4} molar solutions of the acids and ethyl esters (Table III).